

Stereochemistry of Some Alicyclic Ring-Systems. A Preliminary Note.

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The recent investigations of Hückel and his collaborators (*Annalen*, 1925, **441**, 1, and subsequent papers) on the strainless nature of the decahydronaphthalene ring raise the question whether simpler monocyclic ring-systems also possess a similar strainless configuration as suggested by Sachse (*Ber.*, 1890, **23**, 1363), and developed later on by Mohr (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1918, **98**, 315; 1922, **103**, 316). According to them, one would expect that monosubstituted *cyclohexane* derivatives should exist in two stereoisomeric forms, while disubstituted *cyclohexane* compounds would be capable of existing in four isomeric modifications according as the *cyclohexane* ring possess the boat-(Fig. I) or the chair-(Fig. II) shaped configuration.

Fig. I.

Fig. II.

But up till now, no evidence of such compounds appears to have been recorded in the literature. On the other hand, the experimental observations, on purely chemical ground, suggest that *cyclohexane* is a monoplanar ring; in fact the unusual stability of *cyclohexane-spirocyclopropane-2:3-dicarboxylic acid* (I) led Beesely, Ingold and Thrope (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, **107**, 1080) to discard the hypothesis of the strainless *i.e.* the multiplanar configuration

of the *cyclohexane* ring and to assume that it has a uniplanar arrangement. Later on Baker and Ingold (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 123, 122) observed that *cycloheptane* ring exerts an influence which cannot be explained on the assumption of the *monoplanar configuration* for it. And this led them to reconsider the matter and finally to accept the views of Sachse and Mohr on the subject, with this modification that while *cycloheptane* and higher-membered rings behave like true strainless system, the *cyclohexane* molecule is a vibrating framework of the two strainless forms (Figs. I and II) and the resultant effect exerted by it is similar to that of a uniplanar ring. If this were the case, one would expect that by introducing substituents at any two carbon atoms of the *cyclohexane* ring, the free vibration of the molecule would be prevented to some extent and it may then be possible to obtain evidence in support of the *multiplanar configuration* of the ring; and in this connection it is proposed to undertake the elucidation of the following points, namely:

(i) An examination of the stability of the *cyclopropane* ring in *p*-methyl*cyclohexane*-*spirocyclopropane*-2:3-dicarboxylic acid (II) will be made in order to see, if the stability is of the same order as that of *cyclohexane*-*spirocyclopropane*-2:3-dicarboxylic acid (I) or similar to those of its *cycloheptane* and *cyclopentane* analogues (III) and (IV) respectively.

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

(ii) To synthesise the ketoglutaric acids similar to *p*-methyl-*cyclohexane*-1-oxalyl-1-acetic acid (V), and to study the action of concentrated caustic potash solution on it, to find out whether like

its *cyclohexane* analogue, it passes into the *cyclol*-derivative (VI) or is stable like the corresponding *cyclopentane* compounds.

(iii) To examine whether by increasing the number, as well as the molecular volume of the substituents, it is possible to isolate the number of stereoisomeric forms of the same compound, as necessitated on the assumption of the strainless configuration.

(iv) To examine whether a monocyclic ring-system is capable of being interconvertible into a higher or a lower membered ring and if so with what ease and to what extent the interconversion can be effected (*cf.* Meerwein and Schafer, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1922, ii, 104, 289).

In the case of *p*-methylcyclohexanone, some interesting results have already been obtained; the work, however, is not yet complete. A detailed description of it will be published later on. In the mean time for various reasons, it seemed desirable to publish a preliminary note on the subject.

In this connection, I desire to express my indebtedness to Professor J. F. Thorpe, C.B.E., F.R.S., for allowing me to carry on this work, which is so much allied to his classical researches on the stability of *spiro*-compounds.

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